

Cours d'été

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Cours :

Natural law

Professeur :

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Sujet :

Is Aquinas' doctrine of natural law fallacious with regard to the Moore's naturalistic fallacy and Hume's ought/is criterion?

11 août. 21

Grille d'évaluation

Devoir

Attention :

Tableau réservé à l'appréciation du correcteur ou de la correctrice. A remplir par une X.

Ce tableau est suivi d'un espace de commentaires à l'attention de l'étudiant/e.

Critères	Excellent	Satisfaisant	En cours d'acquisition	Non- satisfaisant
Aspect formel et style				
- Syntaxe et orthographe. - Mise en page. - Clarté de la rédaction et relecture.				
- Notes de bas de page et citations. - Bibliographie.				
Structure du devoir				
- Respect de la méthodologie. - Organisation de l'argumentation				
Maîtrise de la matière				
- Problématisation. - Bonne compréhension du cours.				
Approche Critique				
- Recherche documentaire. - Élaboration de la réflexion, positionnement. - Pertinence des arguments.				

Commentaires à l'attention de l'étudiante

Note finale

Nombre de points (1 à 20)	
Qualification LMD (de A à F)	

Barème de qualification LMD :

A : 16-20 points

B : 14-15 points

C : 12-13 points

D : 11 points

E : 10 points

F > 10 points (La qualification F "insuffisant" est attribuée si l'étudiant-e ne remplit pas les conditions préalables ou si le nombre de points est égal ou en dessous de 10).

Veillez trouver, ci-dessous, un tableau de conversion des notes pour chaque pays concerné.

Tableau de conversion des notes

LMD	Fail	E	D	C	B	A						
Austria	Nicht genügend 5	Genügend 4		Befriedigend 3		Sehr gut 1						
Belgium	0 - 9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Czech Republic	> 5	4		3		2		1				
Denmark	0,3,5	6	7		8	9	10	11		12	13	
Finland		1		1.5		2	2.5	3				
France	0 - 9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Germany	6 - 4.3	4 - 3.7	3.3 - 3.0		2.7 - 2.3	2	1.7		1.3	1.0		
Greece	2, 3, 4	5		6	7	8		9		10		
Hungary	1	2		3		4			5			
Ireland	Fail > 39	Third 40 - 49		Lower 2 nd 50 - 59		Upper 2 nd 60 - 69		First 70 <				
Italy	> 18	18 - 23	24 - 26		27 - 28		29 - 30		30 e lode			
Netherlands	> 5	5.5 - 6	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5		9	10	
North America	D-, D, D+, C-	C		C+, B-		B, B+		A-, A, A+				
Norway	IB	3.10 - 3.15	2.95 - 3.05	2.8 - 2.9		2.65 - 2.75			2.15 - 2.6			
Poland	> 1	2		3		4		5				
Portugal	> 9.9	10	11	12	13	14- 15	16	17	18	19 - 20		
Romania	2, 3, 4	5		6	7	8		9		10		
Spain	Suspensio 4	Approbado 5 - 6		Notable 7 - 8		Sobresialente 9		Matricula de Honor 10				
Sweden	U	G or B				G or BA		VG or AB				
Swiss	1 - 3	4				5		6				
United Kingdom	Fail > 39	Third 40 - 49		Lower 2 nd 50 - 59		Upper 2 nd 60 - 69		First 70 <				

**Is Aquinas' doctrine of natural law fallacious
with regard to the Moore's naturalistic fallacy
and Hume's ought/is criterion?**

1. Aquinas' doctrine of natural law and the naturalistic fallacy

1.1. Aquinas' definition of 'goodness'

Since the concept of good is central to Moore's formulation of naturalistic fallacy, we will first examine this notion in the Aquinas.

In the first part of his *Summa*, as a mean to argue that goodness and being are the same, Aquinas gives an essential definition of goodness by stating that "the essence of goodness consists in this, that it is in some way desirable". (*ST* I q.5 a.1) He then continues to clarify his conception of good in the proceeding articles for example that it is perfect and it is actual.

1.2. Aquinas' natural law and the notions of 'good' and 'goodness'

But how 'good' and 'goodness' is related to his formulation of (moral/ethical) natural law? The concept of good "is the first thing that without qualification falls within the understanding of practical reason". (*ST* I-II q.94 a.2) The concept of 'good' appears in his 'first principle of natural law': seek good and avoid evil. For Aquinas, good has the same role as the immediate understanding of being and nonbeing which leads to the first principle of theoretical reason: the principle of non-contradiction. In his view, "humans have an inclination for good"¹ and under an unperverted reason "all the thing for which humans have natural inclination"² are good. In sum, the concept of good is present in his definition, ordination and teleology of the natural law.³ For Aquinas "the good is prior to right": whether an action is right is based on whether that action is good or realizes a good. [1] Furthermore, existence of somethings universally and naturally

¹ Ibid.

² Ibid.

³ Knowledge, society, life and procreation are what Aquinas counts as good; the decisive feature of them for Aquinas is that they are desirable for an unperverted reason.

good is essential for the natural law position. These factors force us to attempt for a definition of ‘good’.

1.3. Moore’s naturalistic fallacy⁴

In *Principia Ethica* [2], Moore coins the term ‘naturalistic fallacy’ for what he considers a confused identification of good. Moore is of the opinion that ethical concepts are irreducible. He states:

“Ethics aims at discovering what are those other properties belonging to all things which are good. But far too many philosophers have thought that when they named those other properties, they were actually defining good; that these other properties were simply not ‘other’ but absolutely and entirely the same with goodness. This view I propose to call the ‘naturalistic fallacy’...”

In short, “a person commits the naturalistic fallacy if he or she identifies some evaluative property⁵ with some naturalistic⁶ or metaphysical property⁷”. [3] For example, one who says that goodness is pleasantness; he is claiming that an evaluative property (goodness) is the same with a naturalistic property (pleasantness). Hence, he has committed the naturalistic fallacy. In other words, “the naturalistic fallacy is the claim that good is definable, that is, the goodness can be identified with a group of simple properties that compose it” [4], therefore for Moore, ‘good’ is indefinable.

Aquinas to some extent identifies the evaluative property of goodness with desirability, perfection and actuality; which are metaphysical properties. To be more exact, he attributes to goodness the essential property of ‘desirability’. I guess Aquinas, in the tradition of Aristotle, may consider the ‘good’ as an ‘indefinable particular’. If this is the case and the ‘desirability’ is not counted as a ‘differentia’ of ‘good’, then Aquinas can not be accused of committing the naturalistic fallacy.

On the other hand, we shall notice that Aquinas does not proceed from a definition of ‘good’ to deductively derive the precepts of natural law one by one. The precepts of Aquinasian natural law, though essentially divine, are more or less normatively

⁴ Whether or not this is a fallacy is disputed.

⁵ Rightness, happiness, etc.

⁶ Properties that can be perceived from the ordinary physical objects and events; they form the subject matter for natural science and psychology.

⁷ God, the absolute, true self, etc.

concluded (not deductively). He uses the notion of ‘good’ to demonstrate the procedure of natural law and its first principle rather than to deduce its explicit content. Beside he regards each of the first practical principles as *per se notum* (self-evident) and *indemonstrabile* (one that cannot be deduced). These considerations are in favour of ‘indefinability of good’ for Aquinas.

2. St. Thomas’s doctrine of natural law and Hume’s ought/is criterion

2.1. Hume’s ought/is criterion

In *Treaties on Human Nature* [5], Hume expresses his surprise “to find, that [in every system of morality] instead of the usual copulations of propositions, *is*, and *is not*, I met with no proposition that is not connected with an *ought* or an *ought not*. This change is imperceptible; but is, however, of the last consequence.” He adds that since *ought/ought not* statement is “new relation or affirmation, ‘tis necessary that it should be observed and explained; and at the same time that a reason should be given some new relation or affirmation, ‘tis necessary that it should be observed and explained; and at the same time that a reason should be given, [...], how this new relation can be a deduction from others, which are different from it.” He is assured “that this small attention would subvert all the vulgar systems of morality”.

The kernel of the argument is based on “the meta-logical doctrine, almost universally accepted in the Early modern period, that in a logically valid argument the conclusion is contained within the premises. Hence if there is a non-logical content in the conclusion that is not in the premises the inference is invalid.” [6] This will be the case, for example, when one deduces moral statements (‘One ought not to kill’) *solely* from non-moral premises such as those concerning the existence of God and human affairs.

We shall note that, “Hume was not denying that the moral can be defined in terms of the non-moral. He was merely denying the existence of logically valid arguments from the non-moral to the moral.”⁸ [7] Thus, Hume’s ought/is criterion is *not* incompatible with naturalism (of Aquinas). “Hume himself was a naturalist, since he supposed that there are moral truths which are made true by natural facts, namely facts about what human beings are inclined to approve of.” [7]

⁸ Without use of ‘the analytical bridge’

2.2. Can the ought/is criterion be used against Aquinas?

Aquinas is sometimes accused of this type of inference. However, if we adhere to a narrow definition⁹ of ‘deduction’ and ‘inference’ there are *no* explicit use of this kind of reasoning in Summa. On the other hand, he is of the opinion that first principles are *per se notum* and *indemosntrabile*. [8] Aquinas never declares syllogistically that ‘one ought not to kill’ because ‘God exists’. Rather, for him the understanding of ‘one ought not to kill’ is a consequence of the immediate perception of ‘good’. However, it might be argued that the ought/is reasoning is build-in in his metaphysics of morals (i.e. metaethics). A metaethics in which we have a model of ‘natural nature’ of human being and in which moral judgements should conform to this nature to be just. Hence, normativity is intrinsic to this type of metaethics. This criticism¹⁰ can be applied to the ethical doctrine of Aquinas, as well as that of Hume.

My opinion is that in metaethics, the so called ‘ought/is fallacy’ is not a fallacy as it is in logic. It seems that demonstration and verification of moral rules will essentially include appeal to nature and norms. I think the critics should illustrate that first, the ‘ought/is criterion’ is a fallacy and then, that it is *also* a fallacy in metaethics.

But why Hume claim that “that this small attention would subvert all the vulgar systems of morality”? I think “this small attention” does not refer only to inferring ought from is¹¹, but rather to the use of this fallacy in the context of the relevant section¹². The entire consideration of the section¹³ leads him to conclude that “vice and virtue is not founded merely on the relations of objects, nor is perceived by reason.” That virtue and vice is not perceived by reason is what put him in opposition to other systems of morality, of Aquinas included. It shall be noted that the precepts of Aquinas’ natural law are perceived self-evidently by unperverted ‘reason’.

Bibliography

⁹ In their logical/ arithmetical sense

¹⁰ First, it must be demonstrated that this criticism is justly founded; it seems not.

¹¹ This fallacy in its purely logical context was known before Hume.

¹² Part I, Section I : “Moral distinction not derived from reason”

¹³ Ibid.

- [1] M. Murphy, «"The Natural Law Tradition in Ethics",» [En ligne]. Available: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2019/entries/natural-law-ethics/>.
- [2] G. E. Moore, *Principia Ethica*, Cambridge University Press, 1993.
- [3] F. Feldman, «The Naturalistic Fallacy: What It Is, and What It Isn't,» chez *Naturalistic Fallacy*, S. Neil, Éd., Cambridge University Press.
- [4] S. Neil, «The Naturalistic Fallacy and the History of Metaethics,» chez *The Naturalistic Fallacy*, S. Neil, Éd., Cambridge University Press, p. 17.
- [5] D. Hume, «A Treatise on Human Nature,» Selby-Bigge, Éd., Clarendon Press, pp. 469-470.
- [6] C. Pigden, chez *The Naturalistic Fallacy*, N. Sinclair, Éd., Cambridge University Press, p. 75.
- [7] C. Pigden. [En ligne]. Available: https://philosophynow.org/issues/83/Hume_on_Is_and_Ought.
- [8] J. Finnis, «Aquinas' Moral, Political, and Legal Philosophy,» [En ligne]. Available: <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2021/entries/aquinas-moral-political/>.